

Foucault's Resistance to Biopolitics

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ABSTRACT

One of the most topical issues in bioethics is the concept of medicalisation. In order to deal with this issue, it is impossible to ignore Michel Foucault's analysis of the subject. The French philosopher is a reference point for all those attempting to reflect on and undertake research into this field. Foucault's importance in this topic lies in his having traced the structural trajectory with which to understand the very construction of medicalisation. In particular, he understands medicalisation not as a phenomenon that springs from other situations but as a framework of meaning to understand human phenomena. Its ascent begins the moment medicine becomes social, when it starts to concern an ever-increasing range of issues, so leading to an absolutisation of health which is nothing more than a normative way of understanding specific vital parameters. This shift loses all reference to regulations, thus becoming the key to grasping the naturalness of man, which at the same time allows human existence to be normalised. For this reason, medicine becomes the instrument of a technique of power – biopolitics – which, by acting on the discipline of the individual to secure the population and achieve regulation over it, so dominates life entirely.

Keywords: Biopolitics; Medicalisation; Biomedicalisation

According to Foucault, medicalisation can be explained by following specific logical steps: health - normalisation - biopolitics - medicalised subjectivity.^[1] The latter is what Foucault claims to be the heart of medicalisation, since without the possibility of the subject recognising the truthful and universal meaning of medicine and the codes it establishes, it could not exist. He follows this by identifying the analysis of subjectivity as central to his philosophical interest, underlining how, in contemporary times, it is produced by and subjected to the mechanism of medicalisation itself. To render this transformation, the French philosopher investigates the mechanism of sexuality,^[2] a situation that causes individuals to regard themselves as subjects of sexuality in need of medical and therapeutic assistance. The importance of sexuality and the studies conducted on it are fundamental, as Foucault uses them to outline the mechanism through which subjectivity is free to think of itself as a function of medicine, causing the subject to become a subject of desire. This also allows for the establishment of the discipline of psychiatry, which stands as the ultimate weapon in establishing the division between normal and abnormal attitudes. It reveals that the apex of biopolitical attitude is established through medicalisation; by acting on the individual and taking into account human expression and social functions, it allows for the safety of the population.

^[3] In short, it can be seen that the phenomenon of medicalisation, sometimes described as a situation in which non-medical problems begin to be treated as medical problems, does not warrant such a simple definition. Some believe that medicalisation results from a frame of meaning, since it was formed out of capitalism and cannot be separated from it.^[4] Foucault, through his analyses, subverts this line of thought, showing how the medicalisation of society paves the way for the establishment of capitalism, while claiming that capitalism itself is what reinforces a medicalised frame of meaning.

For this reason, he argues that in order to oppose medicalisation, it is impossible to follow demedicalisation mechanisms; it is impossible to create institutional forms that differ from medicine, as doing so increasingly legitimises medicalisation. He cites examples in support of this thesis; the first is the birth of psychoanalysis, which, far from freeing man from psychiatry-derived medicalisation, instead forced him into a new form of medicalisation that also includes the analysis of the unconscious.^[5] Secondly, he speaks of anti-psychiatry, the movement that affirmed a desire to consider the universality of human rights. These forms of resistance, according to Foucault, while forming a useful approach to combat the old ways of understanding power as sovereign, do not help in opposing the biopolitical mechanism. Within the narrow contemporary framework, scholars who follow a biomedicalisation paradigm^[6] argue that the pinnacle of the medicalisation attitude, i.e. the possibility of choosing and creating bespoke individuals through genetic engineering, can become the instrument which shifts the emphasis from protecting and normalising the population to perpetuating the will of the individual.^[7] In other words, they claim that through human optimisation, genetic engineering can become that which allows biopolitical practice and thus define forms of medicalization^[8] to be resisted. Such a theory does not appear appropriate in resisting the phenomenon of medicalisation, because once again it uses forms of resistance that do not take into account the peculiarities of the mechanism of power inherent in biopolitics.^[9] Specifically, biopolitics acts through the secularisation of the mechanism of Christian confession, allowing for the creation of objectified forms of subjectivity. This provides the possibility of having made-to-measure children, or attempting to use genetic engineering to improve oneself. In this way, it is not free will that is being expressed, but rather a perpetuation of the conditioning that has allowed power itself to create subjectivity. One can grasp how the problem of resistance to medicalisation must be posed as a question of resistance to biopolitics, that is, to the mechanism of power that uses and rationalises a medicalised frame of meaning. In order to do so, one must understand the differences that biopolitics exert on contemporary,^[10] as opposed to previous, practices of power. The point of any question on the possibility of resistance is precisely this: according to Foucault, it is essential above all to understand what mechanism of power we find ourselves in. After this, it is vital to construct the archaeology and genealogy^[11] of the games of truth that lead to the construction of the order of discourse that regulates and normalises our status as subjects. Thus, Foucault's critique^[12] of the elaborated mechanisms of resistance is based on an analysis of power that does not reflect its explanation in today's society. This is not to say that there is no possibility of resisting the biopolitical mechanism, but that such resistance must be thought of differently to those compared with previous forms of domination. Precisely for this reason, what Foucault brings to light in the latter part of his life is the possibility of opposing biopolitics. This is based on the medicalisation of .life, not through classical forms of political resistance but opposing resistance that is based on the rejection of the identity that is assigned to us. Therefore, the forms of political resistance which contrast biopolitics are those which exercise work on the self, leading to the discovery of a mechanism of medicalised subjection that

constitutes our way of surrendering ourselves.^[13] Only through the continuous exercise of these practices will it become possible to construct a form of autonomous subjectivity that can be opposed to biopolitical will. This does not mean that man should not claim universal rights but must develop freedom based on critical work. It is no coincidence that he identifies the role of philosophy as the possibility of creating a critical ontology of the current situation, questioning the forms which make us what we are in order to reveal a practical-critical model,^[14] useful in perpetuating forms of disassociation that can create autonomous and free subjectivity. Resistance to biopolitics thus derives from work on the self that allows us to constitute ourselves as autonomous subjects who refuse to be reduced to subjugated objects. This is a task of philosophy, which, just as the attitude of *parrhesia*^[15] in the ancient world, must undergo continuous work on itself which can never be said to be either finished or universal. It cannot be finished since the rejection of subjectivity and the establishment of one's subjectivity passes through a perennial questioning of one's self; secondly, such a critique of self can neither be objectivised nor standardized, since it must work on the different forms of reality which present themselves from day to day. Thus, it can be said that resistance to biopolitics can occur due to two factors: firstly, the archaeological and genealogical description of ways which establish the truth of the present and the subject, and secondly an exercise of the critical form of ourselves which allows us to reject what we are in order to ward off those instances of medicalisation and normalisation that perpetuate the same mechanism of medicalization.^[16] These two instances of resistance are tasks that the practical-critical philosophy theorised by Foucault must set itself. It is this which allows for the analysis, critique and courage which are indispensable for a subjective awareness of the modes of resistance to biopolitical power^[17] that can never be generalized and which arise through everyday work in a local sphere.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares that she has no commercial associations (e.g. consultancies, stock ownership, equity interest, patent/licensing arrangement etc.) that might pose a conflict of interest in connection with the submitted article.

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